

Supplementary Figures and Tables

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Supplementary Figures

Gene Ontology (GO) Enrichment Summary

Figure 1: Causal DMRs mapped to biological process GO terms. Top 20 terms by associated causal DMR count are shown; full table provided in [Table 1](#).

Bootstrap ROC-AUC Difference Distributions

Figure 2: Bootstrap distributions of ROC-AUC differences (causal versus SHAP) for Logistic Regression.

Figure 3: Bootstrap distributions of ROC-AUC differences (causal versus SHAP) for Random Forest.

Observed Test ROC–AUC by Feature Set and Model

Figure 4: Side-by-side bar plot of observed test ROC–AUC for logistic regression and random forest across feature sets.

Feature Count vs Performance

Figure 5: ROC-AUC versus number of features (log scale) for logistic regression and random forest across causality-based, SHAP-based, and statistically reduced feature sets.

Supplementary Tables

Full GO Enrichment Results

Table 1: GO terms with associated causal DMR and gene counts

GO term	Causal DMRs	Genes
regulation of gene expression	19	8
signal transduction	17	7
nervous system development	14	5
generation of neurons	13	4
neurogenesis	13	4
central nervous system development	12	4
forebrain development	11	3
brain development	11	3
neuron differentiation	10	3
intracellular signal transduction	9	5
neuron migration	9	2
regulation of signal transduction	8	5
neuron development	8	2
behavior	8	2
positive regulation of gene expression	8	2
response to stress	7	2
central nervous system neuron differentiation	6	1
hindbrain development	6	1
response to cytokine	6	1
forebrain generation of neurons	6	1
regulation of neuron projection development	6	1
learning or memory	6	1
forebrain neuron differentiation	6	1
regulation of neuron differentiation	6	1
neuron fate commitment	6	1
neuron projection guidance	6	1
negative regulation of nervous system development	6	1
positive regulation of nervous system development	6	1
cellular response to cytokine stimulus	6	1
negative regulation of neurogenesis	6	1

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GO term	Causal DMRs	Genes
positive regulation of neurogenesis	6	1
cognition	6	1
regulation of nervous system development	6	1
regulation of neurogenesis	6	1
neuron projection morphogenesis	6	1
negative regulation of neuron differentiation	6	1
positive regulation of neuron differentiation	6	1
cell morphogenesis involved in neuron differentiation	6	1
neuron projection development	6	1
regulation of intracellular signal transduction	4	3
negative regulation of signal transduction	4	2
immune system process	3	3
positive regulation of intracellular signal transduction	3	2
positive regulation of signal transduction	3	2
peripheral nervous system development	2	1
immune system development	2	1
small GTPase-mediated signal transduction	2	1
feeding behavior	2	1
canonical NF-kappaB signal transduction	1	1
vesicle-mediated transport	1	1
chemical synaptic transmission	1	1
positive regulation of neuron apoptotic process	1	1
regulation of canonical NF-kappaB signal transduction	1	1
regulation of neuron apoptotic process	1	1
positive regulation of canonical NF-kappaB signal transduction	1	1
modulation of chemical synaptic transmission	1	1
neuron apoptotic process	1	1